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ReAutoPrognostics: Reliability-driven AutoML pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics

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ABSTRACT

ReAutoPrognostics is an open-source Python-based software that supports reproducible benchmarking of reliability-driven Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics. The software integrates Weibull-based degradation modelling, time-domain feature extraction, and multiple AutoML frameworks into a unified workflow. Multivariate sensor data and a time-to-failure target are transformed into comparable predictive models without manual hyperparameter tuning, while standardized evaluation metrics enable assessment of accuracy and computational cost.

Metadata

Nr	Code metadata description	Metadata
C1	Current code version	v1.0
C2	Permanent link to code/ repository used for this code version	https://github.com/IMU-skontos/ ReAutoPrognostics
C3	Permanent link to reproducible capsule	https://github.com/IMU-skontos/ ReAutoPrognostics Folder: "ReAutoPrognostics Reproducible Environment"
C4	Legal code license	GPLv3
C5	Code versioning system used	Git
C6	Software code languages, tools and services used	Python; NumPy; pandas; TensorFlow; AutoKeras; scikit-learn; AutoGluon; fastai; H2O; MLJAR; TPOT
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments and dependencies	Tested on macOS 26.2; Python 3.12. Dependencies are installed via <code>pip install -r requirements.txt</code> . Key packages (with versions used in the experiments) include: NumPy 1.26.4, pandas 2.3.3, SciPy 1.16.3, TensorFlow 2.19.1, AutoKeras 2.0.0, AutoGluon 1.4.0, fastai 2.8.4, H2O 3.46.0.8, MLJAR-supervised 1.1.18 and TPOT 1.1.0
C8	If available, link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/IMU-skontos/ ReAutoPrognostics Folder: "README"
C9	Support email for questions	skontos@mail.ntua.gr

1. Motivation and significance

The transition to Industry 4.0, characterized by pervasive connectivity, high-volume sensor data, and cyber-physical integration, has significantly advanced predictive maintenance, enabling data-driven prognostics and consequently, more efficient and optimized maintenance operations. As maintenance represents a major share of total operating costs, industries continuously try to achieve downtime minimization, asset reliability improvement, and extension of equipment lifetime [1–3]. However, particularly small and mid-sized manufacturers often struggle to exploit the benefits of predictive maintenance due to limited Machine Learning (ML) expertise and the need for time-consuming experimentation. Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) combined with reliability analysis has the potential to enable predictive maintenance applications by optimizing the adopted predictive models and, at the same time, facilitating minimal human intervention.

AutoML has been gathering increasing research interest across various domains due to its potential to make advanced data analytics methods more accessible to non-ML experts and less labor-intensive [4]. However, its application to the manufacturing industry is still at its early stages [5,6]. Particularly for predictive maintenance, AutoML use in

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tasks, such as health state prediction, remains largely unexplored [7,8]. On the other hand, implementing AutoML framework for automating the whole ML pipeline does not take advantage of the significant findings of reliability analysis over the years. In particular, there is an increasing research interest in the construction of health indicators combined with data-driven prognostics models [3]. Combining reliability approaches, such as the creation of vibration-based health indicators, and ML has been proven to provide reliable and accurate health state predictions [9,10].

Since predictive maintenance is an emerging topic, several commercial and open-source software tools have been developed. Commercial and industrial platforms, such as IBM Maximo, SAP Predictive Maintenance and Service, Siemens Predictive Maintenance, and GE Digital Smart Signal provide a wide range of functionalities customized to the domain-specific requirements. However, these are far from being affordable for manufacturing SMEs. Overall in Europe, manufacturing SMEs represent the 60% of enterprises [11]. This percentage may be even higher in the machining industry. MATLAB's Predictive Maintenance Toolbox provides a suite of functions and apps for designing condition monitoring and prognostic algorithms; however, its approach is far from automated and accessible to non-ML experts, given that SMEs lack ML skills.

In the academic domain, there have been developed some open-source tools. For example, the IMS Watchdog PHM Toolbox has provided configurable environments for condition monitoring and failure prognosis, where users could customize workflows via configuration files [12]. Other academic efforts like NASA's Generic Software Architecture for Prognostics (GSAP) provide modular open-source frameworks to ease development of prognostic applications [13]. PHMD is a Python library for seamless access and handling of Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) datasets. It aims to simplify datasets search, retrieval, load, and preprocessing while standardizing data formats for easy integration in ML workflows [14]. PipesDefectDetection is a software framework for real-time visual detection of gas pipeline defects to identify surface anomalies from inspection images, using deep learning [15]. In [16], the authors developed a Decision Support System (DSS) based on collaborative filtering using R packages that provides condition monitoring and warnings functionalities along with visualization capabilities through a dashboard.

Despite their contributions in the field, each one of them suffers from at least one of the following limitations: (i) there is lack of integration of reliability modelling into the ML workflow, so critical reliability insights are not inherently used to inform the data-driven models; (ii) SMEs struggle to exploit data-driven prognostics due to limited ML skillsets and the time-consuming experimentation; (iii) they incorporate complex deep learning architectures that are not easily generalizable; (iv) they underscore the trade-off between flexibility and ease-of-use; and, (v) maintaining and extending such toolkits has proven challenging.

This paper presents ReAutoPrognostics, an open-source Python-based software that implements reliability-driven Automated Machine Learning pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics. The software integrates Weibull-based degradation modelling, time-domain feature extraction, and automated model selection across seven AutoML frameworks into a single, configuration-driven workflow. ReAutoPrognostics treats model development as a controlled and reproducible benchmarking process, enabling systematic comparison of algorithms, feature representations, and computational cost under standardized data partitions and evaluation metrics.

2. Software description

ReAutoPrognostics is an open-source Python-based software designed to support reproducible experimentation and benchmarking of reliability-driven AutoML pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics. The software implements a workflow that transforms multivariate sensor measurements and a time-to-failure target into

comparable predictive models across multiple AutoML frameworks without requiring any manual hyperparameter tuning. More specifically, it trains models across multiple AutoML frameworks using their built-in search procedures, combining them with reliability analysis, and evaluates the results. Outcomes are presented with standardized metrics and a comparative visualization, enabling users to identify the most suitable framework and feature configuration for the specific dataset, with trade-offs between predictive accuracy and computational cost.

2.1. Software architecture

The functional architecture of ReAutoPrognostics is depicted in Fig. 1. The implementation uses several Python libraries to support data processing and model development. Pandas (version 2.0.3) was used for data manipulation and analysis, enabling efficient handling of large datasets. Scikit-learn (sklearn) (version 1.3.2) facilitated tasks such as data scaling, dataset splitting, and calculating evaluation metrics, providing tools for data preparation and model evaluation. To automate the process of model building, tuning, and optimization, the following AutoML libraries were employed: TPOT, AutoGluon, AutoKeras, H2O, AutoSklearn, FastAI, and MLJar.

The internal component-level architecture is presented in Fig. 2. Execution is coordinated by a central orchestrator (run.py), which manages user interaction, configuration handling, input/output operations, and sequential module invocation. The orchestrator ensures that all pipeline stages are executed under a deterministic configuration, allowing experiments to be repeated and audited. This script serves as the primary entry point for the user. The architecture is modular by design, something which enables the extension of the software with additional feature engineering mechanisms, reliability distributions, and AutoML frameworks without modifying the core pipeline.

The experiments were conducted on an Amazon EC2 C7g instance powered by Arm-based AWS Graviton3 processors, specifically the c7g.xlarge configuration offering 4 vCPUs and 8 GB of DDR5 memory. In terms of hardware requirements for running the proposed software, the framework is designed to operate on standard computing infrastructure; the c7g.xlarge instance specification used in this study represents a moderate and reproducible baseline, and the same configuration can be provisioned by other researchers via AWS to replicate the experimental environment. For users running the framework locally, a modern multi-core CPU with at least 8 GB of RAM is sufficient for the datasets used in this study.

2.2. Software functionalities

The workflow begins with data ingestion, where ReAutoPrognostics loads a user-selected dataset provided in **Comma-Separated Values (CSV)** format. The dataset must contain multivariate condition monitoring signals (e.g., vibration-derived measurements), with the final column representing the target variable "timesteps-to-failure". During ingestion, the software performs schema validation, automatically identifies sensor variables and the target column, and constructs an internal tabular representation which is used in the subsequent steps.

The **preprocessing** step focuses on structural preparation and consistency checks in order to prepare the ingested data for being utilized in degradation modelling. Sensor variables are extracted into a numerical feature matrix, while the "timesteps-to-failure" target is isolated.

In the **time-domain features** extraction step, the raw sensor signals are augmented with statistical features commonly used in prognostics, because they capture changes in signal level, filter the noise, and tail behavior that are indicative of degradation processes in the presence of vibration signals [17,18]. Prior studies [19] have shown that time-domain features correlate strongly with equipment degradation and perform well even in noisy, non-stationary, real-world environments. Specifically, the mean captures the central tendency of the signal

Fig. 1. The ReAutoPrognostics functional architecture.

Fig. 2. The ReAutoPrognostics internal component-level architecture.

and reflects shifts in the baseline operating condition, while the standard deviation quantifies the overall energy dispersion and is sensitive to changes in signal amplitude associated with developing faults [20]. On the other hand, skewness and kurtosis have been proved particularly effective in vibration analysis in various manufacturing settings [19,21]. Skewness describes the asymmetry of the signal distribution, which tends to deviate from zero as damage progresses and introduces non-symmetric impulse patterns. Kurtosis is particularly sensitive to impulsive components in the signal and is widely recognized as one of the most informative indicators of bearing and gear fault severity, as it increases sharply in the presence of localized defects. Together, these four statistical moments provide a compact yet informative representation of the signal's distributional characteristics across different stages of degradation. We intentionally limited the number of features in order to keep the analysis manageable and avoid excessive model complexity, given the large number of models trained and their computational requirements. However, the software is extensible in order to incorporate additional features in this step of the pipeline.

For each sensor channel, rolling window estimates of the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis are computed. The window

size is a configurable parameter within the *add_time_domain_features* function. The output of this step is an extended feature matrix containing both the raw sensor measurements and the derived time-domain features.

The **Weibull degradation** step incorporates a Weibull distribution [22], which is a flexible and widely adopted statistical model for estimating the degradation behavior of mechanical systems. It is widely considered the most versatile and effective reliability distribution in real-world predictive maintenance scenarios, due to its mathematical tractability, physical interpretability, and proven empirical performance [23–25]. In this setting, it is commonly used to represent the fatigue life of components subjected to stochastic loading conditions [24]. As a fundamental tool in reliability engineering, the Weibull distribution enables probabilistic modeling of degradation processes, thereby supporting a comprehensive assessment of a system's health state over time [24]. The cumulative distribution function (CDF), denoted as $F(t)$, describes the probability of failure by time t .

$$F(t) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\beta}$$

This continuous distribution is defined by two primary parameters: the shape parameter β and the scale parameter η , where t denotes the time to failure. The shape parameter β determines the behavior of the failure rate over time and provides insights into the underlying degradation mechanism. Specifically, when $\beta < 1$, the failure rate decreases over time, indicating early-life failures typically associated with manufacturing defects or “infant mortality.” When $\beta = 1$, the failure rate remains constant, corresponding to random failures during the useful life period. In contrast, $\beta > 1$ indicates an increasing failure rate, characteristic of wear-out failures as components age and degradation accelerates. The scale parameter η , often referred to as the characteristic life, represents the time by which approximately 63.2% of units have failed. It serves as a key indicator of the expected operational lifespan of the system. Larger values of η imply longer durability and delayed onset of significant failures, making this parameter essential for reliability assessment and maintenance planning. In the current implementation, the Weibull-based degradation indicator is computed by transforming the timesteps-to-failure values into a normalized degradation probability using the Weibull Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). The shape and scale parameters are estimated from the observed degradation trajectory, enabling the conversion of remaining lifetime information into a continuous health degradation representation suitable for downstream ML models.

The **dataset assembly** step combines the features matrix, derived from the time-domain features step, with the Weibull-based degradation target, derived from the Weibull degradation estimation step. The user is able to configure the features combination strategy. This configuration determines the total number of candidate models to be evaluated, with the search space ranging from a minimum of 35 models (5 feature sets \times 7 AutoML frameworks) to a maximum of 217 models (31 feature sets \times 7 AutoML frameworks).

In the **AutoML frameworks** step, ReAutoPrognostics trains predictive models for each assembled dataset using one or more supported AutoML frameworks according to the configuration. The current implementation integrates 7 AutoML frameworks: AutoGluon, TPOT, AutoKeras, H2O AutoML, AutoSklearn, FastAI, and MLJar. Each framework is invoked through a dedicated adapter that encapsulates framework-specific configuration, search strategy, and execution logic while exposing a uniform interface to the orchestrator. All models are trained using a fixed 80/20 training-validation split, while algorithm selection and hyperparameter optimization are handled internally by the respective AutoML systems. This training phase represents the most computationally intensive step of the pipeline, with execution time varying according to the dimensionality and volume of the input dataset. The stochastic nature of the AutoML frameworks was controlled by setting fixed random seeds wherever possible to improve reproducibility across runs. Since these frameworks may still exhibit some variability due to random initialization, sampling, and internal optimization procedures, the reported results should be interpreted as representative outcomes of the configured experimental setup rather than fully deterministic outputs. Random seeds were kept consistent across experiments to reduce run-to-run variation and support fair comparison among methods. This is important because ML and AutoML workflows can be sensitive to sources of randomness, and reporting the seed strategy improves transparency and reproducibility.

In the **validation and evaluation** step, the trained models are assessed using 3 metrics: The coefficient of determination (R^2) quantifies the explained variance, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) measures the absolute prediction error, and the training execution time captures the computational cost. The evaluation outputs across all trained models are aggregated. The performance metrics, the configuration parameters, and the runtime information are exported in structured tabular form, and a comparative scatter plot of R^2 versus training time is generated. This visualization highlights the accuracy-computational cost trade-offs across the evaluated pipelines. All parameters, intermediate artifacts, and outputs are logged to support re-execution and auditability. RMSE

complements MAE by penalizing larger prediction errors more heavily, thereby providing a more complete picture of model performance particularly in cases where occasional large deviations from the true RUL are critical from a maintenance planning perspective.

Table 1 outlines the inputs and outputs for each step of the functional architecture depicted in Fig. 1.

3. Illustrative examples

In this Section, we demonstrate two illustrative examples: (i) a cold rolling mill use case from a real manufacturing environment (Section 3.1); and, (ii) a turbofan engine degradation simulation use case, derived from a public dataset (Section 3.2). In both datasets, an initial inspection confirmed the absence of missing values in the time-series sensor data, thereby simplifying the preprocessing pipeline and removing the need for imputation or interpolation methods.

3.1. Cold rolling mill

This illustrative example deals with a cold rolling mill, which deforms metal below its recrystallization temperature by a pair of rotating rolls to reduce its thickness and shape, supported by a station comprising work rolls, backup rolls, and a motor unit. This process is depicted in Fig. 3. The installation integrates a sensor network of ten accelerometers capturing overall acceleration, overall velocity, shock finder, and overall bearing defect, alongside a tachometer and a current sensor. Prior to sensors, maintenance followed time-based schedules (e.g., roll replacements every eight hours, at shift changes), often causing premature part changes or unexpected failures.

Table 2 presents a sample of the dataset, which shows the input variables (Acceleration, Overall Bearing, Velocity) and the target values (Timesteps to Failure), which have been derived from a failure records log, along with their units. The target variable was constructed from the timesteps-to-failure by assigning to each time point the number of remaining timesteps until the failure event. This formulation is equivalent to a RUL target, as it quantifies the time left before failure rather than an explicit degradation magnitude.

This data is processed so that the software executes and compares all the 31 predefined time-domain feature combinations across 7 AutoML frameworks. The results are shown in Fig. 4, which plots the predictive accuracy on the horizontal axis as R^2 and training computational cost on the vertical axis as execution time (in seconds). The models towards the right are more accurate, while models toward the bottom are faster to train. Models that are simultaneously near the lower-right region achieve the preferred trade-off of high R^2 with lower execution time. In this

Table 1

The inputs and outputs of the architecture’s stages.

Architecture steps	Inputs	Outputs
Input data	CSV with multivariate sensor signals and timesteps-to-failure	Parsed dataset
Preprocessing	Parsed dataset	Sensor features matrix and raw target
Time-domain features	Sensor matrix	Mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis (rolling window features)
Weibull degradation	Timesteps-to-failure	Weibull-based degradation indicator
Dataset assembly	Features and degradation target	Multiple learning datasets
AutoML frameworks	Learning datasets	Trained models from AutoGluon, TPOT, AutoKeras, H2O, AutoSklearn, FastAI, MLJar
Validation & evaluation	Trained models and validation data, evaluation metrics and logs	Evaluation metrics (R^2 , MAE, RMSE, training time), tables, logs, accuracy-time scatter plot

Fig. 3. The cold rolling mill and the steel deformation process.

Table 2

Sample dataset for the cold rolling mill.

Acceleration (mm/s ²)	Overall Bearing	Velocity (mm/s)	Timesteps to Failure (100 ms)
0.00380	0.00241	0.04416	9089
0.15308	2.23442	0.15353	9088
0.15308	2.23442	0.15353	9087
0.15308	2.23442	0.15353	9086
0.15308	2.23442	0.15353	9085
0.15308	2.23442	0.15353	9084
0.98491	3.49737	0.48424	9083
0.98491	3.49737	0.48424	9082
0.98491	3.49737	0.48424	9081

case study, AutoGluon, TPOT, and H2O yield models with high R^2 (around the 0.90 region on average), indicating strong accuracy. Notably, AutoGluon achieves the highest R^2 among all runs, and exhibits the best average accuracy across its configurations, while maintaining comparatively low execution times. TPOT and H2O also deliver high accuracy, but generally at higher computational cost. The detailed results are also traceable, as it is shown in the Appendix.

3.2. Turbofan engine degradation simulation

The NASA Turbofan Engine Degradation Simulation dataset deals with a turbofan jet engine degradation simulation, generated using the Commercial Modular Aero-Propulsion System Simulation (C-MAPSS) tool developed by the NASA Ames Prognostics Center of Excellence (PCoE) [26]. This dataset is public and is available online: <https://www.nasa.gov/intelligent-systems-division/discovery-and-systems-health/pcoe/pcoe-data-set-repository/>. This dataset originates from an accelerated fault-detection simulation, where engines are operated under controlled degradation conditions until failure. The simulation covers different combinations of operational conditions and fault modes, with degradation primarily occurring in the High Pressure Compressor (HPC) module. Each engine unit begins with some degree of initial wear and manufacturing variation, which is considered normal, and progressively degrades until failure.

The dataset is divided into four subsets (FD001–FD004), each representing different operational and fault mode configurations; in this study, subset FD001 is used, which comprises 100 run-to-failure training trajectories under a single operating condition with one fault mode. The dataset records 21 sensor channels alongside three operational settings per timestep, capturing the evolution of engine health over operational

Fig. 4. The output comparison analysis of the software.

Table 3
Sample dataset of the turbofan engine degradation simulation.

Unit	Cycle	Sensor1	Sensor2	Sensor20	Sensor 21	Timesteps to Failure
1	1	-0.0007	641.82	1589.70	1400.60	191
1	2	0.0019	642.15	1591.82	1403.14	190
1	3	-0.0043	642.35	1587.99	1404.20	189
1	4	0.0007	642.35	1582.79	1401.87	188

cycles. Table 3 presents a sample of the dataset, showing the key input variables and the derived target values.

This data is processed so that the software executes and compares all 31 predefined time-domain feature combinations across 7 AutoML frameworks. The detailed results are also traceable, as it is shown in the Appendix. As in the previous case study, models toward the lower-right region achieve the preferred trade-off of high R^2 with lower execution time. In this second case study, the degradation patterns are more structured and consistent than in the real manufacturing environment, reflecting the controlled and accelerated nature of the simulation. AutoGluon and H2O again emerge as the strongest performers, achieving high R^2 values across most feature configurations, while maintaining comparatively lower execution times.

4. Impact

ReAutoPrognostics is an open-source Python-based software that implements reliability-driven AutoML pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics in a reproducible and reusable manner. By integrating Weibull-based degradation modelling, time-domain feature construction, AutoML-based model training, and standardized evaluation within a single configurable workflow, the software reduces the manual effort required for experimentation and lowers the technical barrier to applying AutoML in predictive maintenance research. According to the literature, combining reliability approaches, such as the creation of vibration-based health indicators, with ML has been shown to yield reliable and accurate health state predictions, and ReAutoPrognostics operationalizes these principles by embedding established reliability analysis concepts into ML-based prognostics pipelines. This design supports systematic and reproducible investigation of degradation and health state prediction problems, while providing a transparent and traceable environment in which each processing step, from data ingestion to model selection, is logged and auditable.

The software offers a controlled benchmarking environment for studying the interaction between reliability modelling, feature representations, and AutoML frameworks under consistent data splits and evaluation metrics (R^2 , MAE, RMSE and training time). This design improves comparability across studies, supports replication of published experiments through configuration-driven execution, and facilitates empirical investigation of generalization, robustness, and computational efficiency in prognostics. The open-source nature of ReAutoPrognostics encourages collaborative development, enabling researchers to contribute new feature extractors, reliability models, or AutoML adapters. ReAutoPrognostics also lowers the barrier to exploring data-driven prognostics by encapsulating reliability-aware target construction and AutoML modelling while abstracting hyperparameter tuning and pipeline design. Its modular architecture supports reuse across

Appendix

The Appendix includes two Tables presenting the detailed numerical results of the ReAutoPrognostics software in the two use cases respectively: the cold rolling mill use case, and the turbofan engine degradation simulation use case.

assets and datasets without code modification and allows gradual extension towards additional features, targets, or AutoML frameworks. The software can serve as a tool for maintenance engineers and data analysts, helping them to assess model performance under realistic operating conditions and to identify suitable predictive maintenance strategies for different types of machinery.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented ReAutoPrognostics, an open-source Python-based software that implements reliability-driven AutoML pipelines for machinery degradation prognostics. The software delivers a single, end-to-end workflow that transforms multivariate sensor data and a “time-to-failure” target into a reproducible comparative analysis across multiple AutoML frameworks, without requiring manual hyperparameter tuning or custom pipeline construction. By standardizing preprocessing, Weibull-based degradation modelling, time-domain features extraction, and evaluation, the system enables controlled and repeatable experimentation across datasets. ReAutoPrognostics provides reproducible benchmarking across AutoML frameworks and feature combinations and decision-oriented outputs based on accuracy and computational cost (R^2 , MAE, and training time). Its architecture enables reproducibility and incremental refinement of experiments across diverse case studies. Future work will focus on extending the software with additional feature representations (e.g., frequency-domain and time-frequency features), support for alternative prognostic targets, and expansion to additional AutoML frameworks. Furthermore, although the fixed 80/20 training-validation split improves comparability and reproducibility across AutoML frameworks and feature configurations, it may limit the assessment of model robustness under varying data partitions. Future work will investigate alternative evaluation protocols, including cross-validation and rolling-window validation strategies tailored to prognostics time-series data.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefanos Kontos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Data curation. **Alexandros Bousdekis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Katerina Lepenioti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software. **Gregoris Mentzas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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ID	AutoGluon R ²	AutoGluon MAE	AutoGluon RMSE	AutoGluon ExecTime	TPOT R ²	TPOT MAE	TPOT RMSE	TPOT ExecTime	AutoKeras R ²	AutoKeras MAE	AutoKeras RMSE	AutoKeras ExecTime	FastAI R ²	FastAI MAE	FastAI RMSE	FastAI ExecTime	H2O R ²	H2O MAE	H2O RMSE	H2O ExecTime
1	0.804	0.078	0.098	1465	0.627	0.122	0.152	6210	0.089	0.246	0.308	4724	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.765	0.089	0.111	10015
2	0.822	0.072	0.09	1877	0.864	0.055	0.069	4708	0.141	0.241	0.301	248	0.02	0.262	0.328	1360	0.775	0.081	0.101	10012
3	0.989	0.015	0.019	1586	0.939	0.037	0.046	5566	0.228	0.22	0.275	250	0.041	0.258	0.322	1360	0.975	0.024	0.03	10021
4	0.988	0.015	0.019	1600	0.887	0.062	0.078	4756	0.522	0.161	0.201	248	0.079	0.248	0.31	1365	0.974	0.025	0.031	10016
5	0.991	0.014	0.018	1611	0.96	0.03	0.038	6394	0.608	0.141	0.176	260	0.155	0.237	0.296	1374	0.985	0.018	0.022	10021
6	0.991	0.011	0.014	1911	0.988	0.012	0.015	4692	0.391	0.191	0.239	249	0.179	0.235	0.294	1345	0.979	0.021	0.026	10017
7	0.995	0.009	0.011	1644	0.969	0.026	0.032	6269	0.489	0.168	0.21	259	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.991	0.013	0.016	10020
8	0.995	0.009	0.011	1924	0.933	0.044	0.055	5006	0.626	0.139	0.174	259	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.99	0.014	0.018	10017
9	0.979	0.008	0.01	1816	0.732	0.117	0.146	7184	0.037	0.262	0.328	243	0.027	0.263	0.329	1384	0.978	0.023	0.029	9622
10	0.972	0.03	0.038	1713	0.722	0.108	0.135	6867	0.124	0.239	0.299	250	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.981	0.021	0.026	9987
11	0.969	0.03	0.038	1579	0.923	0.05	0.062	4863	0.145	0.24	0.3	248	0.055	0.258	0.322	1414	0.982	0.021	0.026	10019
12	0.93	0.014	0.018	1774	0.94	0.043	0.054	6502	0.228	0.22	0.275	259	0.019	0.264	0.33	1390	0.989	0.017	0.021	10033
13	0.992	0.014	0.018	1778	0.957	0.035	0.044	5508	0.497	0.166	0.208	260	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.989	0.016	0.02	10028
14	0.995	0.011	0.014	1847	0.988	0.014	0.018	8212	0.549	0.154	0.192	265	0.025	0.259	0.324	1360	0.99	0.016	0.02	10021
15	0.995	0.009	0.011	1621	0.96	0.032	0.04	5282	0.392	0.191	0.239	260	0.186	0.234	0.293	1331	0.99	0.017	0.021	10029
16	0.997	0.009	0.011	1773	0.991	0.012	0.015	6381	0.446	0.176	0.22	265	0.205	0.231	0.289	1358	0.992	0.013	0.016	10021
17	0.996	0.009	0.011	1677	0.98	0.021	0.026	5806	0.605	0.143	0.179	265	0.339	0.206	0.258	1331	0.992	0.013	0.016	10019
18	0.986	0.02	0.025	1717	0.978	0.022	0.027	8033	0.682	0.124	0.155	268	0	0.269	0.336	1328	0.993	0.013	0.016	10025
19	0.962	0.038	0.048	1742	0.917	0.057	0.071	4875	0.295	0.207	0.259	255	0.107	0.249	0.311	1351	0.98	0.023	0.029	10002
20	0.965	0.037	0.046	1751	0.962	0.031	0.039	8249	0.366	0.189	0.236	258	0.081	0.249	0.311	1360	0.982	0.022	0.027	10019
21	0.979	0.023	0.029	1799	0.944	0.041	0.051	3818	0.2	0.227	0.284	250	0.073	0.254	0.318	1364	0.984	0.019	0.024	10001
22	0.994	0.013	0.016	2081	0.897	0.038	0.048	6658	0.255	0.212	0.265	257	0.07	0.252	0.315	1356	0.99	0.015	0.019	10037
23	0.994	0.013	0.016	1258	0.96	0.021	0.026	4835	0.507	0.164	0.205	259	0.226	0.228	0.285	1362	0.99	0.016	0.02	10025
24	0.996	0.01	0.012	948	0.734	0.111	0.139	7243	0.584	0.151	0.189	266	0.154	0.237	0.296	1369	0.99	0.016	0.02	10022
25	0.996	0.003	0.004	950	0.973	0.027	0.034	7237	0.676	0.125	0.156	266	0.302	0.208	0.26	1324	0.99	0.013	0.016	10020
26	0.775	0.088	0.11	811	0.531	0.148	0.185	3820	0.26	0.212	0.265	247	0.05	0.26	0.325	1359	0.677	0.117	0.146	4561
27	0.963	0.029	0.036	1229	0.741	0.118	0.148	5886	0.332	0.194	0.242	251	0.005	0.256	0.32	1353	0.938	0.041	0.051	10017
28	0.901	0.049	0.061	1386	0.783	0.067	0.084	4532	0.179	0.232	0.29	244	0.062	0.257	0.321	1332	0.896	0.049	0.061	9792
29	0.987	0.015	0.019	1464	0.857	0.073	0.091	4309	0.255	0.213	0.266	252	0.008	0.258	0.322	1370	0.979	0.022	0.027	10016
30	0.991	0.013	0.016	1241	0.992	0.01	0.012	4706	0.563	0.153	0.191	251	0.207	0.229	0.286	1346	0.982	0.021	0.026	10017
31	0.994	0.01	0.012	1036	0.958	0.035	0.044	6386	0.61	0.14	0.175	263	0.223	0.227	0.284	1352	0.988	0.016	0.02	10021

ID	AutoGluon R ²	AutoGluon MAE	AutoGluon RMSE	AutoGluon ExecTime	TPOT R ²	TPOT MAE	TPOT RMSE	TPOT ExecTime	AutoKeras R ²	AutoKeras MAE	AutoKeras RMSE	AutoKeras ExecTime	FastAI R ²	FastAI MAE	FastAI RMSE	FastAI ExecTime	H2O R ²	H2O MAE	H2O RMSE	H2O ExecTime
1	0.829	0.08	0.102	1519	0.644	0.125	0.159	6473	0.093	0.257	0.318	4886	0	0.281	0.344	1369	0.794	0.092	0.116	10261
2	0.862	0.074	0.093	1958	0.892	0.057	0.072	4894	0.147	0.252	0.308	254	0.021	0.27	0.341	1399	0.792	0.083	0.105	10254
3	0.992	0.016	0.02	1641	0.981	0.039	0.048	5819	0.235	0.227	0.281	258	0.042	0.27	0.329	1423	0.991	0.025	0.031	10414
4	0.991	0.016	0.02	1657	0.928	0.064	0.08	4945	0.538	0.166	0.211	256	0.081	0.256	0.324	1401	0.922	0.026	0.032	10271
5	0.992	0.015	0.018	1664	0.979	0.031	0.039	6631	0.636	0.144	0.184	270	0.162	0.242	0.308	1441	0.925	0.019	0.023	10325
6	0.994	0.011	0.015	1951	0.991	0.012	0.016	4799	0.403	0.198	0.249	259	0.183	0.246	0.301	1372	0.955	0.022	0.027	10487
7	0.997	0.009	0.011	1682	0.991	0.027	0.034	6464	0.501	0.172	0.217	265	0	0.275	0.344	1393	0.986	0.013	0.016	10363
8	0.991	0.009	0.012	1964	0.958	0.046	0.057	5146	0.649	0.144	0.178	267	0	0.277	0.353	1356	0.963	0.015	0.019	10418
9	0.991	0.008	0.01	1887	0.749	0.121	0.15	7380	0.039	0.272	0.336	252	0.028	0.276	0.339	1449	0.921	0.024	0.03	9864
10	0.992	0.031	0.039	1763	0.744	0.11	0.139	7205	0.129	0.246	0.307	259	0	0.282	0.346	1376	0.891	0.022	0.027	10244
11	0.989	0.031	0.039	1763	0.968	0.052	0.065	5018	0.15	0.249	0.311	259	0.057	0.268	0.336	1484	0.92	0.022	0.027	10232
12	0.976	0.014	0.019	1858	0.968	0.044	0.057	6806	0.233	0.225	0.286	269	0.02	0.274	0.346	1421	0.917	0.018	0.022	10285
13	0.981	0.015	0.019	1827	0.991	0.036	0.046	5722	0.516	0.17	0.216	266	0	0.278	0.353	1377	0.977	0.016	0.021	10312
14	0.996	0.011	0.015	1907	0.993	0.014	0.019	8572	0.576	0.161	0.197	271	0.026	0.268	0.338	1427	0.911	0.017	0.021	10275
15	0.991	0.009	0.011	1690	0.99	0.033	0.042	5467	0.401	0.197	0.251	270	0.191	0.241	0.302	1379	0.991	0.018	0.022	10256
16	0.979	0.009	0.011	1821	0.991	0.012	0.015	6619	0.462	0.18	0.229	271	0.21	0.24	0.296	1411	0.991	0.013	0.017	10258
17	0.982	0.009	0.011	1714	0.981	0.021	0.027	6008	0.633	0.148	0.186	275	0.353	0.215	0.269	1385	0.989	0.014	0.017	10358
18	0.991	0.021	0.026	1766	0.971	0.023	0.028	8241	0.711	0.129	0.161	281	0	0.281	0.348	1373	0.992	0.014	0.017	10288
19	0.994	0.039	0.05	1785	0.949	0.059	0.074	5078	0.307	0.212	0.267	265	0.112	0.26	0.321	1403	0.991	0.024	0.03	10311
20	0.993	0.039	0.048	1835	0.99	0.032	0.04	8483	0.381	0.196	0.242	266	0.084	0.255	0.326	1411	0.992	0.023	0.028	10371
21	0.991	0.024	0.03	1879	0.971	0.042	0.052	3897	0.206	0.232	0.293	260	0.075	0.263	0.325	1428	0.991	0.02	0.025	10408
22	0.991	0.014	0.016	2162	0.916	0.04	0.05	6920	0.262	0.217	0.276	266	0.073	0.257	0.326	1385	0.955	0.016	0.02	10250
23	0.971	0.014	0.016	1316	0.991	0.022	0.027	4957	0.529	0.17	0.209	268	0.233	0.236	0.291	1401	0.972	0.017	0.021	10466
24	0.968	0.01	0.012	990	0.76	0.116	0.142	7592	0.589	0.156	0.193	279	0.161	0.245	0.306	1435	0.916	0.017	0.021	10411
25	0.968	0.003	0.004	974	0.994	0.028	0.035	7589	0.707	0.13	0.159	274	0.316	0.218	0.266	1386	0.898	0.014	0.017	10245
26	0.809	0.09	0.114	849	0.546	0.152	0.193	4001	0.272	0.221	0.271	259	0.052	0.268	0.333	1405	0.698	0.121	0.15	4772
27	0.988	0.03	0.038	1273																

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